

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

Deliverable: D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

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D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

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Disclaimer

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

NEANIAS develops thematic services for EOSC communities in the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The project will integrate the thematic services into the EOSC ecosystem after they reach the maturity required by EOSC. At the same time, the project is investigating the possibility of onboarding a number of core services to EOSC as well, thus exceeding the targets initially set for the availability of NEANIAS services on EOSC marketplace.

This deliverable presents the results of EOSC integration activities realised by the time of its preparation. The progress of EOSC integration activities is compared against the plan presented in Deliverable D8.3 “EOSC integration plan (final)” [1], elaborated in August 2021. It also introduces the appropriate changes to the EOSC integration plan in order to ensure its consistency with the updated plans of NEANIAS service providers (both thematic and core ones) as regards the onboarding of their services to EOSC.

1. Introduction

NEANIAS is an EU funded project, which aims to develop and integrate services to EOSC in the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The objective of integration is to share these thematic services with scientific researchers of EOSC communities on these fields.

This deliverable reports on the results of EOSC integration activities realised by the time of its preparation. The progress of EOSC integration activities is compared against the plan presented in Deliverable D8.3 “EOSC integration plan (final)” [1], elaborated in August 2021. At the time of writing this deliverable, the project has already onboarded six (6) thematic services to EOSC marketplace, while five (5) additional thematic services are to be made available on EOSC marketplace by Q1 2022. At the same time, the project is investigating the possibility of onboarding a number of core services to EOSC as well, thus exceeding the targets initially set for the availability of NEANIAS services on EOSC marketplace. One (1) core service has already been onboarded to EOSC. The service onboarding process is facilitated by WP8, as regards procedural and management issues, and WP7, as regards the technical aspects of the integration process.

This deliverable has been written based on the current EOSC landscape, which is a continuously evolving environment, and provides up-to-date information as regards several fields related to EOSC integration, such as architecture, interfaces, access mechanism, federated services and so on.

The final accomplishments of NEANIAS activities towards EOSC integration will be reported in Deliverable D8.5 “EOSC integration activities report (final)” of the project, to be submitted in M32 of the project.

The structure of this document is as follows: Section 2 makes a brief introduction to the targeted EOSC integration activities, as these were presented in Deliverable D8.3 of the project. Section 3 presents the results of EOSC integration activities at the time of writing this deliverable and discusses any deviations and changes to the integration plan presented in Deliverable D8.3. Finally, the conclusions are presented in Section 4.

2. Integration plan to EOSC

2.1. NEANIAS services to be integrated to EOSC

The following section introduces the NEANIAS services that will be integrated into EOSC. These services will cover three major research sectors; Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. Beyond these thematic services, NEANIAS develops/provides Core services in four (4) groups; C1 covers Open-Science lifecycle support services, while C2 covers EOSC hub, RIs and cloud integration enabling services, C3 covers AI and C4 covers Visualization services. C1 and C2 provide basic services to enable integration of the thematic services in NEANIAS, i.e. not services targeting reuse by 3rd parties, therefore they will not be onboarded to EOSC and as such they are not presented in detail in this section. On the other hand, the C3 and C4 services support the delivery of NEANIAS thematic services, and their integration to EOSC is optional, based on the plans of the respective providers.

2.1.1. NEANIAS thematic services

2.1.1.1. Underwater services

Underwater surveys have numerous scientific and commercial applications in the fields of archaeology, geology, biology, and energy involving tasks such as ancient shipwreck prospection, ecological studies, environmental damage assessment, and detection of temporal changes. NEANIAS is developing the following underwater services that will be onboarded to EOSC:

- **U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data**

The UW-BAT (Bathyprocessing) service provides a large number of MB-System tools to post-process vendor specific raw data. Its approach is to create digital terrain models (DTM) and maps from multibeam echosounder (MBES) raw data.

- **U2 - Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data**

The Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data (UW-MOS) service deals with optical mapping in underwater environments. UW-MOS provides an operational solution for large area representation of the seafloor also addressing visibility limitations from the underwater medium.

- **U3 - Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data**

The Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data (UW-MAP) service delivers a user-friendly cloud-based solution integrating cutting-edge machine learning frameworks for mapping several seabed classes, validated for archaeological, geo-hazards, energy, and other applications.

2.1.1.2. Atmosphere services

NEANIAS Atmosphere services aim to address operational studies related to the atmosphere and engineering tasks to involve diverse user communities linked to the atmosphere. The sectors they target include, among others, meteorologists, industrial air pollutant emitters, ecologists, rural urban planners and air quality authorities, geohazards, civil protection,

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insurance or health agencies. NEANIAS is developing the following atmosphere services that will be onboarded to EOSC:

- **A1 - Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring**

The Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring (ATMO-FLUD) service provides a set of algorithms for the calculation of flux densities of Sensible Heat, Latent Heat, Turbulent Kinetic Energy and other scalars like GHGs. The input data to the service is user provided although test data are available for trial runs. Real data should be experimentally obtained by the user bearing in mind that the fundamental method employed in this service is the “Eddy Covariance”.

- **A2 - Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions**

A2 service consists of two sub-services; the ATMO-SEISM and the ATMO-STRESS services.

- ATMO-SEISM is a service for scientists to design, develop and test the correlation between gas measurements, atmospheric conditions and earthquake data.
- ATMO-STRESS shows regional trends on 2-D gridded map (x-y plane) and can reconstruct a paleostress trajectory map by implementing the following two different methods (Lee and Angelier, 1993): (i) polynomial and (ii) distance weighted interpolation.

- **A3 - Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting**

The Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting (ATMO-4CAST) service allows the generation of meteorological forecasts by using the Weather Research and Forecast Model.

2.1.1.3. Space services

The Space services deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions to industrial stakeholders, e.g. aerospace engineering and related technology companies, but also national space agencies and public outreach bodies, e.g. space museums and planetariums.

The latest NEANIAS release includes seven services tailored to the Space sector user requirements and driven by three clusters of common functionalities, i.e.: S1 - FAIR Data Management and visualization for complex data and metadata, S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional images, S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques:

- **S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata**

S1, namely “SPACE-VIS” services, provide required functionalities that enable efficient and scalable visual discovery, exposed through advanced interaction paradigms, such as the visual analytic, also exploiting virtual reality starting from software modules such as the ViaLactea framework, Astra Data Navigator and the ADAM platform.

- **S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional image**

S2, namely “SPACE-MOS” services, deliver multi-dimensional space maps through novel mosaicing techniques (i.e. stitching of multidimensional images/maps with

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overlapping fields of view) to a variety of prospective users/customers (e.g., mining & robotic engineers, mobile telecommunications, space scientists) starting from software modules such as Montage, ISIS3, ASP and the ADAM Data Processing System.

- **S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques**

S3, namely “SPACE-ML” services, deliver structure detection capabilities addressing the researchers’ needs to identify and classify, in an efficient way, specific structures of interest starting from software modules such as CAESAR, CUTEX, VLFF and well-known machine learning and deep learning algorithms and methods.

2.1.2. NEANIAS core services

2.1.2.1. C3 Artificial Intelligence services

C3 Artificial Intelligence services form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering features of a typical Machine Learning (ML) workflow lifecycle, and that are also intended for composition of higher-level services. The EOSC integration of C3 services is optional; current integration plans and achievements are presented in Section 3.1. NEANIAS is developing the following services in this area:

- **C3.1 AI Science Gateway: service for development of ML models using Jupyter Hub**

A development environment is necessary for the researchers to design, prototype, implement and test AI powered solutions. To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, the popular IPython based Jupyter Hub project is preferred, with TensorFlow and Keras libraries. Researchers are able to prototype solutions, while computationally intense training can be loaded to a computational cluster. Results can be visualized using the Visualization gateway (C4.2).

- **C3.2 Serving trained ML models**

Accessing trained models as web services should be possible seamlessly, with low efforts. To deploy a model as an API, large amount of memory is necessarily allocated and used constantly. Technically, there are multiple approaches to implement model serving, user and researcher-friendliness is prioritized. The fundamental idea behind model serving is that authorized clients are able to access prediction functionality without directly accessing the model, which would create a serious overhead caused by data transfer and memory allocation. Instead, a RESTful API based communication is preferred between a model server and the client. The server implements the model, allocates memory to efficiently handle prediction, and listens for input parameters on the interface. On request, prediction is done using the inner implementation, and the results are responded to the client.

- **C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod**

The training of deep neural networks on large amount of data requires a significant amount of processing time, which could be reduced by using GPU accelerators. The next step in increasing the performance is by using multiple GPU-enabled nodes in a distributed environment. While the parallel processing of deep neural networks has its limitations, Horovod [2] is a robust tool which can be used to scale the training of TensorFlow based network implementations.

- **C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML**

In addition to models based on neural networks (that can benefit from a multi-GPU deployment, especially for learning phases) that are managed through C3.3, other AI techniques for classification, regression, or clustering tasks can however benefit from a deployment and execution in a distributed and memory-based architecture such as the one offered by Spark. In particular, C3.4 will support a variety of machine learning models such as Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and ensemble models (Random Forests and Gradient Boosting) for both classification and regression, clustering algorithms, and other support functions that are useful in real-world, large scale, machine learning pipelines. The set of basic ML algorithms and models can also be extended by means of creative parallel computing approaches (e.g. parallel implementations of DBSCAN algorithm on top of Spark, an algorithm which is not natively provided by MLib, are known and available).

2.1.2.2. C4 Visualisation services

C4 services, namely “visualisation services” in the context of NEANIAS, form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering features of a typical visualisation workflow lifecycle, and that are also intended for composition of higher level services. The EOSC integration of C4 services is optional; current integration plans and achievements are presented in Section 3.1. NEANIAS is developing the following services in this area:

- **C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery (VD)**

C4.1 provides tools to support data intensive computing for visual scientific discovery (including research training and outreach) for observational data, theoretical simulations and 2D/3D tiling and maps. C4.1 consists of three distinct high-performance services for visual analytics from multidimensional data tables (VD-VisIVO), high-quality volume rendering of particle-based datasets exploiting a variety of parallel programming models leveraging upon heterogeneous infrastructures (VD-Splotch) and creation of interactive 2D/3D tilings and maps (VD-Maps).

- **C4.2 Visualisation Gateway (VG)**

C4.2 provides a development environment for designing, rapid prototyping, implementing and fully testing complex visualisation solutions for realising common data exploration workflows. C4.2 services are envisaged to be interconnected with C3.1 to visualise AI powered solutions, C4.3 to underpin powerful VR/AR solutions and C4.4 to facilitate end-user data accessibility. C4.2 services are deployed in a way that is fully embedded within the relevant workflows of end-user activities, while exploiting diverse parallelisation models and infrastructure accelerator capabilities.

- **C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)**

C4.3 provides a toolkit underpinning an environment for designing, implementing and testing complex visualisation solutions exposed to end-users via Cross Realities (XR) mechanisms, e.g. those based on Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). C4.3 exploits the framework for visual discovery developed in C4.1. C4.3 services are envisaged to be interconnected seamlessly with C4.2 to furnish complex visualisation workflows and C4.4 to underpin advanced data access. As part of the XR toolkit

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various VR/AR viewers are expected to be realised visualising not only space objects but also 3D data of various typologies of interest to other NEANIAS domains (e.g. atmospheric).

- **C4.4 Spatial Data Stores (DS)**

Spatial data stores allow data to be referenced, queried and retrieved, based on a given location (e.g. the globe, the Earth, planetary bodies with a proper reference system or the sky).

2.2. Targeted EOSC Services for integration

Based on the investigation of the services listed in Section 2.1.1, we identified the following services/support as requirements to integrate the thematic services to EOSC:

- Providers and Service modelling based on EOSC Provider and Resource profiles. This choice aims to facilitate the onboarding of NEANIAS providers and services in the EOSC portal, complying with the existing standards and EOSC guidelines.
- Authentication and authorization
- Monitoring
- Accounting – As described in D8.3 [1], the EOSC offered Usage Accounting Service primarily focuses on infrastructure level assets and services. The NEANIAS approach to the task, through the NEANIAS Accounting Service takes a more fine-grained approach, letting individual services define their own accountable resources and respective actions.
- Helpdesk – The Helpdesk requirements for the NEANIAS service offerings are addressed through the NEANIAS offered Helpdesk functionality under the Service Management System (SMS) defined processes and tools. Still, the approach taken is chosen so that future integrations with the EOSC Helpdesk remains an option.
- Data Management Planning
- Data Catalogue

In this section, we introduce the available EOSC services in these categories and how and to what extent they will be integrated with NEANIAS services.

2.2.1. EOSC Portal

NEANIAS aims to deliver thematic services to researchers via EOSC, therefore the registration of these services in the EOSC Portal is a compulsory step. EOSC offers an API that allows service providers to push information to EOSC directly from their systems or service catalogues. The use of this API is within our plans since the beginning of this project so as to avoid updating the same information in two different systems; the NEANIAS catalogue portal and the EOSC portal. However, some restrictions on the use of the API arise from EOSC, which necessarily will be respected by NEANIAS; the API cannot be used for the initial registration of a service provider or for the onboarding of the first service of a provider. On the other hand, the API allows the onboarding of additional (i.e. apart from the first one) services of a specific provider and facilitates the update of information of already onboarded services.

2.2.2. Federation Services

In this subsection, existing EOSC federation services, which we plan to directly integrate with the NEANIAS services or have been thoroughly taken into account in order to achieve future integration, are introduced.

2.2.2.1. AAI services

The NEANIAS project includes in its offering the NEANIAS AAI service that offers a horizontal solution for all NEANIAS services to cover the common requirements of authenticated access, whether it comes in the form of a direct user request or as cross service invocations. The NEANIAS AAI service in its core supports identity federation through well-established standards and protocols, including Open ID Connect (OIDC) and SAML.

Using these standards and protocols, the NEANIAS AAI service acts as an integration point with the EOSC Portal offered AAI. This integration will allow EOSC-trusted users to be offered access to NEANIAS resources. As the number of EOSC-trusted identity providers expands, the NEANIAS AAI will also expand its reach to a wider user base, regardless of the end user supporting Identity Provider.

This approach also allows the NEANIAS AAI service to extend the network of federation of supported identity providers, providing seamless authenticated access to trusted users via widely used and accepted standards.

From a technical standpoint, integration with EOSC AAI is straightforward. However, NEANIAS AAI has to face the legal complexity of passing user information to the services it is being used by. As such it requires a special “terms of use” statement that is currently under legal review and will be submitted to EOSC for the final integration of the service.

2.2.2.2. Availability and reliability monitoring

Availability monitoring is a service where users and service providers can check the status of an EOSC service and get information about its availability and reliability in the selected time period. NEANIAS services are being integrated with the ARGO monitoring platform [3] for this purpose. At the time of writing this deliverable, this integration is ongoing in order to cover all the NEANIAS thematic services.

Moreover, ARGO monitoring is being complemented by the NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure, local to the GARR Cloud facilities, to allow the implementation of different types of monitoring, such as whitebox monitoring.

2.2.2.3. Accounting

As mentioned in Deliverable D8.3 [1], NEANIAS usage accounting strategy has a substantially different perspective than the one that EOSC main accounting offering captures. Furthermore, there are challenges pertaining to sensitive data management that substantially hinder the usability of a 3rd party service for tracking usage data. Despite this misalignment, EOSC accounting remains relevant for specific purposes, as NEANIAS services eventually consume storage and computing capacity from underlying provider(s). Measuring those (on a per provider and per user basis) helps the project build the picture of its operational costs and plan sustainable business model for beyond the project lifetime. Currently this is performed by NEANIAS Accounting Service, however the EOSC Accounting system can be also helpful. It

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could support delivering a certain level of information about computing and storage use under the same umbrella as other EOSC services do.

Presently, the project proceeds with the internal accounting solution and monitors the situation, in order to respond to any need of changing its policy.

2.2.2.4. Helpdesk

To assist and support the end users of the NEANIAS offered Services, a ticketing system is made available, acting as the entry point for service consumers to report issues, incidents and requests in a structured fashion. This ticketing system, formally named “NEANIAS service management IT system”, is the NEANIAS Helpdesk system and supports the collection of:

- Incident Reports - Unplanned disruption of operation in a service or service component, or degradation of service quality versus the expected or agreed service level or operational level.
- Service Requests - User request for information, advice, access to a service, etc.

The NEANIAS Helpdesk processes and functionality, as defined within the context of the Service Management System (Deliverable D8.2 “EOSC service model” [4]), aim to cover the NEANIAS users’ needs for support and communication with the respective service providers.

Although not a mandate within the NEANIAS description of action, the opportunity to integrate the NEANIAS Helpdesk with the EOSC Helpdesk may be beneficiary for the end users in providing a more streamlined support experience. To this end, the following integration options offered from the EOSC Helpdesk can be investigated for future integration:

- Ticket Redirection: Use the EOSC helpdesk only as a contact point to redirect the entry request for the specific service to a mailing list.
- Full Integration: Integrate an external ticketing system with the EOSC helpdesk infrastructure to enable transfer of tickets between them.

2.2.3. Research Data Management

In this section we provide an overview of some of the existing EOSC services regarding FAIR data management that we opted to reuse and integrate, so that NEANIAS services are conformant with the Open Data Guidelines [5] and the FAIR principles [6]. As our project moves along and as the EOSC service portfolio expands we will also expand our view and will consider additional research data management services for integration.

2.2.3.1. ARGOS Data Management Plan tool

Argos [7] is an open and extensible EOSC service that simplifies the management, validation, monitoring and maintenance of Data Management Plans. It is a service provided by OpenAIRE, contributed by NEANIAS in its validation stage. Argos allows actors (researchers, managers, supervisors, etc.) to create actionable DMPs that may be freely exchanged among infrastructures for carrying out specific aspects of the Data management process in accordance with the intentions and commitment of Data owners. To facilitate the adoption of the platform, NEANIAS has engaged OpenAIRE experts since the beginning of the project to provide support on the use of the platform both in live presentations and as web training.

In NEANIAS, we exclusively use Argos to maintain our Data Management plans, however no integration is planned with other RDM related service in the scope of the project.

2.2.3.2. Research Data Repository

NEANIAS handles data in its own resources for processing and integrates with well-known data repositories for obtaining data of relevance to its services. Those are handled by each specific thematic service provider. Currently there are no functional requirements that direct service providers to proceed to integration with specific EOSC repositories, however the overall intent of the project to empower Open Science and FAIR data, applies a uniform policy for all its services with respect to data publication.

Zenodo [8], an EOSC service, is the catch-all repository developed and maintained by CERN as part of the OpenAIRE project, in support of Open Science and FAIR principles. Zenodo's aim is to store all of its contents for the lifetime of the repository, providing free access to all metadata under the CC0 license (except for email addresses). Additionally, all metadata can be harvested via the OAI-PMH mechanism for repository interoperability [9]. Moreover, Zenodo offers a REST API [10] to allow applications to:

- a) upload and publish research outputs,
- b) search published records,
- c) upload and download files.

In NEANIAS, we opted to use Zenodo via its REST API for depositing all research product metadata, and for all open-access research data.

2.2.3.3. Research Data Catalogue

Data FAIRness requires that data are searchable by their audience, which in turn, requires that they are properly described and registered. NEANIAS uses Zenodo as its data catalogue and follows the respective metadata description specification. Furthermore, we will organize data under the "community" concept, in order to facilitate their attribution to the project and simplify their discovery when coming from NEANIAS origins.

2.2.3.4. PID infrastructure

Publishing data requires that those can be identified uniquely by their consumers. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are the common construct for that. In NEANIAS, all published datasets will acquire a PID, under the DOI schema. We use Zenodo as a Persistent Identifier (PID) production service to allow NEANIAS services to automatically obtain PIDs for research outputs.

2.3. Service management

As presented in Deliverable D8.2 "EOSC Service Model" [4], NEANIAS chose to develop an IT Service Management System of its own, which is nevertheless compatible with the EOSC one. More specifically, the NEANIAS SMS is developed based on the same service management framework as the EOSC one, i.e. FitSM [11], with ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 extensions [12] (where/if needed), utilising also ITIL guidance [13] as best practice. This way, we aim on one hand to be compliant with the EOSC service management system and on the other hand to establish a more tailored-made SMS, which will better serve the needs of NEANIAS services. Additionally, we aim to have increased control on the SMS, so that we can adjust it more easily and quickly to future developments of the services and needs of the providers of NEANIAS services.

The main tools that support the NEANIAS SMS include the following:

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Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS catalogue portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides the interface to service providers to register and describe their services • Presents information about the services that NEANIAS provides to users • Enables service ordering • Provides the interface to users for submitting incidents and service requests, complaints, requirements about services, etc.
NEANIAS service management IT system ¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors the lifecycle of incidents and service requests, complaints, changes, etc.
NEANIAS wiki	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system

The above tools are complemented by own tools of the thematic/core service providers, which focus on the more technical aspects of service management (e.g. performance monitoring, logging, event management, capacity management etc.).

2.4. Service ordering and pricing

The goal of the task in this period was to better understand the expectations of the providers concerning order management via EOSC, and to specify the actions needed for the implementation of non-trivial ordering scenarios, for example when financial transactions are needed.

The task established the following understanding within the Consortium: NEANIAS services are/should be accessible in EOSC via 4 ways:

1. Open access: The service does not need user authentication/authorisation and can be accessed via redirection from the EOSC Marketplace (MP). The already onboarded NEANIAS services all use this option.
2. Ordering: The service requires an access order from the user. This order is generated by the EOSC MP and sent to the NEANIAS provider who can enable access and approve the order in the MP. The NEANIAS SMS already describes this process, but there is no service yet using it.
3. Ordering with computing resources provided by the user: This would be a new option in which the user must make a compute allocation in EOSC before submitting the NEANIAS order and include the allocation endpoint in the NEANIAS order. The details will be elaborated via a collaboration planned with EGI-ACE (See below).

¹ The NEANIAS service management IT system is developed under WP7 and implements a workflow-type functionality on a ticketing software platform (redmine).

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4. Pay-for-use ordering: This option was assessed separately and is detailed below in paragraph 2.4.1. The conclusion was that this will not be elaborated further in NEANIAS. The providers who need this should register their service with a 'demonstration access' level in EOSC. More complex access has to be negotiated bilaterally with the user outside EOSC/NEANIAS.

2.4.1. Pay-for-use ordering

At the time of writing the NEANIAS proposal it was expected that the EOSC Marketplace would introduce pay-for-use (or other financial transaction) capabilities, which NEANIAS services could rely on. From recent interactions with the EOSC Marketplace team it is understood that the EOSC Marketplace does not have pay-for-use ordering, or any other financial transaction support in its roadmap. One of the reasons for this is that the EOSC implementation roadmap puts academic, free-at-point-of-use resources in its focus until 2023; industry and other sectors are planned only after that.

From D9.3 [14] and from recent discussions within the NEANIAS Consortium it was confirmed that there are a few services in NEANIAS that expect income from pay-for-use transactions beyond the project lifetime. The task had a roundtable discussion about which service provider and why would need pay-for-use or other financial transactions. Two reasons came out from the investigation:

1. Some of the thematic services require big capacity machines for use cases that go beyond a certain input size. Pay-for-use could be an option for those use cases to recuperate the cost of using big machines, however there could be other options, such as shifting the compute intensive workload to external e-infrastructures that are free-at-point-of-use for NEANIAS providers and their users.
2. Some of the thematic service providers are commercial entities and would like to provide their service on a pay-for-use basis in EOSC.

The discussion concluded that we would explore option 1 via an interaction with external e-infrastructures, particularly with the EGI-ACE project that delivers the Compute Platform in EOSC. This is detailed in the next section 2.4.2.

For option 2 the conclusion was that the implementation of a pay-for-use system within NEANIAS would require more effort than the project has, and overall is out of scope for our Description of Action. Experiences show that payments between different countries and legal entities can be complex, and involve finance, legal and technical aspects that are often unique to each institute.

2.4.2. Relying on the EOSC Compute Platform

We assessed the offering of the EOSC Compute Platform provided by EGI-ACE project (<https://www.egi.eu/projects/egi-ace/>) and found it a suitable platform to scale out the NEANIAS services that require external hosting/execution environments. Using the EGI-ACE Open Call mechanism (<https://www.egi.eu/projects/egi-ace/call-for-use-cases>) NEANIAS will submit an application to EGI-ACE by the 15th of December deadline, requesting cloud resources (CPU, GPU, storage) to setup and validate two use cases in the EOSC Compute Platform:

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

1. Scale out compute intensive NEANIAS thematic services to EGI-ACE cloud/Kubernetes resources. The successful validation of this use case would open a new service delivery model for NEANIAS thematic service providers: Their users would have to request compute allocations from the EOSC Compute Platform, and 'bring these allocations' to the thematic service providers who would connect these to their service to serve that individual user.
2. Hosting NEANIAS thematic services in EGI-ACE cloud/Kubernetes resources. The successful validation of this use case would open a new sustainability model for thematic service providers: The thematic service providers could make arrangements with EOSC Compute Platform providers for the hosting of the NEANIAS services beyond the NEANIAS lifetime, and delivering the services as a collaborative effort of NEANIAS and EOSC Compute Platform providers.

The successful validation of these cases would provide a new sustainability path for some of the NEANIAS services (e.g. A2 and U3 providers found this a workable approach). There are, however, cases in NEANIAS where the approach cannot be used: Some services use IP protected codebase and running them (or even part of the service) on external machines is not a viable option.

We expect the following timeline for the EGI-ACE use case submission and implementation:

- Finalise and submit the use case to EGI-ACE: 15th of December 2022
- Getting access to the EGI-ACE resources: January 2022
- Reach first service setups with the use cases: end of March 2022
- Validation of the setups: end of April 2022
- Reach full validation with all the NEANIAS services in scope: end of May 2022 (end of use of EGI-ACE resources)
- Update NEANIAS delivery model in EOSC (incl. User guides), and sustainability models: end of September 2022

3. Status of EOSC integration activities

In this section we present the results of EOSC integration activities as these were realised by the time of writing this document. Integration results are presented vis-à-vis the EOSC integration plan presented in Deliverable D8.3 [1] of the project.

3.1. Onboarding of NEANIAS services to EOSC

NEANIAS activities towards EOSC integration follow an agile approach that is based on successive development cycles, considering the following:

- The cycles bring NEANIAS services from very basic EOSC integration with minimal functionalities to more complex EOSC integration with advanced capabilities.
- We specify the exact content for each cycle considering the situation at that moment when we reach that cycle.
- The cycles can be repeated for the different Thematic Services independently from each other. For example, cycle 1 can start for the most mature thematic service as soon as that thematic service is ready for publication in EOSC. Other thematic services will be considered for cycle 1 once they become mature enough for EOSC.
- Cycle 1 as well as cycle 2 has a set of preparatory steps that NEANIAS should complete before any of the thematic services reach those cycles. These preparatory steps should be completed only one time, while the cycles should be completed one time for each thematic service.

The following tables aim to present the current progress of the EOSC integration activities compared to the EOSC integration plan introduced in Deliverable D8.3 [1].

Preparatory steps for cycle 1 (done once) [Provisional timeline: Started at M3; Finish by M24]

The preparatory steps for cycle 1 have been completed before the elaboration of Deliverable D8.3 in M22, therefore ahead of the envisaged timeline.

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
NEANIAS portal and services catalogue prototype deployment	NEANIAS catalogue portal developed, deployed, and populated with information on NEANIAS providers and services	Completed
NEANIAS service catalogue sign up and registration		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers registration based on EOSC onboarding process 	Providers of NEANIAS services registered on NEANIAS catalogue portal, using EOSC Provider Profile metadata	Completed

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NEANIAS services terms of use definition and acceptance based on EOSC RoP 	Terms of Use and Privacy Policy skeletons have been developed, in order to be reused and customized by each NEANIAS service during EOSC onboarding	Completed
Setup the NEANIAS IT Service Management skeleton where service management documentations can be developed and stored	NEANIAS Service Management System defined in D8.2 Tools supporting the operation of the NEANIAS Service Management System defined (see Section 2.3), and are continuously evolving according to the needs of the NEANIAS services	Completed

Cycle 1 – Make NEANIAS thematic services accessible to EOSC users by following the EOSC onboarding process (done for each thematic service)

[Provisional timeline: Start at M12; Finish by M31 (EOSC catalogue integration and AAI integration by M25 based on D6.1, AAI to be slightly delayed by 1 month for legal issues resolution)]

Cycle 1 activities are in progress for each thematic service independently and follow the maturity of each service.

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
Ensure EOSC RoP compliance (i.e. we are able to fill the EOSC Service Description Template for the NEANIAS thematic service which is in scope)	Providers and Service modelling is based on EOSC Provider and Resource profiles, in order to facilitate the onboarding of NEANIAS providers and services in the EOSC portal and comply with the existing standards and EOSC guidelines	Completed for <u>all</u> services
Define NEANIAS services pricing as well as respective SLA(s) and OLA(s) for the service	SLA(s) and OLA(s) are addressed in the Terms of Use of each service.	Completed for all services already onboarded to EOSC, based on the needs of the service providers.

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
	Pricing of services is under investigation in relation to the sustainability of the services after the end of the NEANIAS project.	See section 2.4
Activate ordering (access requests) from the EOSC Portal to NEANIAS thematic services	An access request mechanism has been developed on the NEANIAS SMS and may be used by NEANIAS services on EOSC that require some type of registration/ authorization. This mechanism is maintained and updated, based on the needs of NEANIAS services.	Setup completed. Activation in progress (as per needs of the services). Currently all NEANIAS services available on EOSC marketplace are open access, thus not requiring the use of an ordering mechanism.
Ensure EOSC access policies and licensing compliance	Terms of Use and Privacy Policy skeletons have been developed, in order to be reused and customized by each NEANIAS service during EOSC onboarding. Access policies and licensing compliance are addressed in the Terms of Use of each NEANIAS service.	Completed for all services already onboarded to EOSC Customisation for the rest of the services: In progress
Enable single sign-on from the EOSC Portal to the NEANIAS Thematic service (through the NEANIAS AAI service)	Integration of NEANIAS AAI service with EOSC AAI service technically finalized: Preparatory work on protocol compatibility, consent management and required integration steps.	Under internal legal preparation of terms of use and privacy statement.
Provide minimum level documentation and helpdesk support for users	Documentation for NEANIAS services is available on the webpages of each service. Helpdesk support is facilitated by helpdesk e-mail addresses and the possibility to use the NEANIAS helpdesk system to	Completed and constantly updated. Hand-over of the NEANIAS helpdesk system to service

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
	submit requests, incidents, complaints, etc.	providers: In progress
Ensure minimum level of user feedback collection and continuous improvement (CRM)	Customer relationship management (CRM) process, and Handling customer complaints (CRM1) and Reviewing customer satisfaction (CRM2) procedures have been established in the context of the NEANIAS Service Management System. Their application to collect feedback by the users of NEANIAS services is in planning stage.	In progress

Preparatory steps for cycle 2 (done once)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
Release the NEANIAS research product catalogue based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform	Completed	Zenodo is provided by CERN and is already an EOSC service. We already created a community named "NEANIAS" for the NEANIAS research products.
Release NEANIAS PID service based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform	Completed	Zenodo is provided by CERN and is already an EOSC service. PIDs are provided as part of the usual CERN publishing process.
Release the NEANIAS Data Validation Service	Under development	Service has been redesigned to better address the needs of the thematic services.

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
Release the NEANIAS Data Publishing Service	In progress, being tested	A component that facilitates publishing to Zenodo is developed and currently undergoes testing, to be released, provisionally, by Q1 2022.
Integrate with OpenDMP deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos	Completed	OpenDMP is published by OpenAIRE Nexus project. NEANIAS is contributing, being among the first pilot projects for it. It is present in EOSC.

Cycle 2 – Enrich NEANIAS services with research product catalogue and data management capabilities (done for each thematic service)

[Provisional timeline: Finish by M32]

Cycle 2 activities are in progress for each thematic service independently, and follow the maturity of each service.

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
Integrate with the NEANIAS research product catalogue based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform	Integration is investigated by each service provider, according to the requirements of its service.	Integration with the service is good practice but not mandatory for NEANIAS services. To facilitate integration, the Zenodo REST API was presented and demonstrated.
Integrate with NEANIAS PID service based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform	Integration is investigated by each service provider, according to the requirements of its service.	Integration with the service is good practice but not mandatory for NEANIAS services. To facilitate integration, the

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
		Zenodo REST API was presented and demonstrated. Additionally, services that integrate with the Data Publishing Service can obtain a PID this way.
Integrate with the NEANIAS Data Validation Service	No programmatic integration is planned.	Programmatic Integration with DVS is optional for services. Users can exploit the DVS independently after publishing data from thematic services.
Integrate with the NEANIAS Data Publishing Service	Integration is investigated by each service provider, according to the requirements of its service.	Integration with the service is good practice but not mandatory for NEANIAS services.
Integrate with OpenDMP deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos	No programmatic integration is planned.	Programmatic Integration with Argos is optional for services. Users can exploit Argos independently after publishing data from thematic services.

Cycle 3 – Improve support for EOSC users based on initial experiences (done for each thematic service)

[Provisional timeline: Finish by M32]

Cycle 3 activities are in progress for each thematic service independently and follow the maturity of each service.

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
Provide FAQs about the services		In progress

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
Activate NEANIAS usage accounting	NEANIAS usage accounting is being activated. Before EOSC onboarding, service providers select how they integrate with the service, according to their accounting requirements. However, the integration is not a prerequisite for EOSC onboarding.	Completed for the services already onboarded to EOSC In progress for the rest of the services
Activate NEANIAS monitoring	NEANIAS monitoring is being activated. Before EOSC onboarding, service providers select how they integrate with the service, according to their monitoring requirements. However, the integration is not a prerequisite for EOSC onboarding.	Completed for the services already onboarded to EOSC In progress for the rest of the services
Integrate NEANIAS Services with EOSC Availability and Reliability monitoring	As the EOSC Availability and Reliability monitoring is designed to be integrated directly with EOSC services, direct integration is in progress for thematic and core services. The NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure is being used to complement the EOSC Availability and Reliability monitoring by, e.g., performing whitebox monitoring tasks.	Two core services have started the integration. Work is in progress to integrate all the thematic services and part of the core services.
Integrate NEANIAS usage accounting with EOSC Accounting	Refinements of NEANIAS accounting features.	No specific integration plan yet.
Define NEANIAS services CRM processes	CRM process and procedures defined as part of the NEANIAS service management framework. Their application to collect feedback by the users of NEANIAS services is in planning stage.	In progress

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Activity (as per final plan in D8.3)	Progress	Status / Comments
Add support for customised SLAs and OLAs		No such needs have been identified based on the characteristics of the services
Improve software documentation	Documentation for NEANIAS services is available on the webpages of each service and is constantly updated.	In progress
Extend NEANIAS Helpdesk	NEANIAS Helpdesk functionality is constantly upgraded to meet the needs of service providers and service users.	By the time of writing this deliverable, NEANIAS Helpdesk has been extended with Service Ordering functionality to accommodate such needs, if/when they arise.

Based on the above, the overall achievements of EOSC onboarding activities are shown in the following table.

Service name	Lead Provider	Expected EOSC onboarding date
THEMATIC SERVICES		
Underwater services		
U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data	TELEDYNE	Q1 2022
U2 - Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data	CORONIS	Onboarded ²
U3 - Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data	ATHENA	Onboarded ³
Atmosphere services		
A1 – Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring	ATHENA	Onboarded ⁴

² <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/uw-mos/details>

³ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/uw-map/details>

⁴ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/atmo-flud/details>

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Service name	Lead Provider	Expected EOSC onboarding date
A2 – Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions		
<i>Atmo-Stress</i>	ATHENA	Q4 2021
<i>Atmo-Seism</i>	ATHENA	Q1 2022
A3 – Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting	UBIWHERE	Q1 2022
Space services		
S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata		
<i>SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service</i>	INAF	Onboarded ⁵
<i>SPACE-VIS ADN Service</i>	ALTEC	Q4 2021 ⁶
<i>ADAM-SPACE</i>	MEEO	Onboarded ⁷
S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional image	MEEO	N/A. Service functionality realized through the Vialactea and ADAM-SPACE services.
S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques		
<i>SPACE-ML CAESAR service</i>	INAF	Onboarded ⁸
<i>SPACE-ML AstroML service</i>	INAF	N/A. Service functionality included in the SPACE-ML CAESAR service.
CORE SERVICES		
C3 Artificial Intelligence services		
C3.1 AI Science Gateway	SZTAKI	N/A
C3.2 Serving trained ML models	ALTEC	N/A
C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod	SZTAKI	Q1 2022
C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML	UNIMIB	Plan for EOSC onboarding under investigation
C4 Visualisation services		

⁵ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/space-vis-vialactea-service>
⁶ Onboarding of the service to EOSC is in progress. At the time of writing this deliverable, the provider has submitted its registration application to EOSC, and waits for the approval from EOSC team to proceed to the registration of the service.

⁷ https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/meeo.adam_space
⁸ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/space-ml-caesar-service/details>

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

Service name	Lead Provider	Expected EOSC onboarding date
C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery (VD)		
<i>VD-VisIVO</i>	INAF	Plan for EOSC onboarding under investigation
<i>VD-Splotch</i>	UoP	Plan for EOSC onboarding under investigation
<i>VD-Maps</i>	CORONIS	Onboarded ⁹
C4.2 Visualisation Gateway (VG)	UoP	Plan for EOSC onboarding under investigation
C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)	ALTEC	N/A
C4.4 Spatial Data Stores (DS)	JACOBS	N/A

At the time of writing this document, six (6) thematic services have already been made available on EOSC marketplace and the onboarding of one more is in progress. Additionally, one core service (C4.1 – VD-Maps) has been onboarded to EOSC.

Comparing the current status and plans to the plan presented in D8.3, we note the following:

- The number of NEANIAS thematic services on EOSC marketplace has increased by one. More specifically the ADAM-SPACE service under S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata has been onboarded to EOSC in December 2021 according to the plan presented in Deliverable D8.3.
- One additional thematic service (SPACE-VIS ADN Service under S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata) will soon be available on EOSC marketplace as the onboarding process is in progress. Onboarding of this service started significantly ahead of the schedule presented in D8.3, where this was expected to take place in Q2 2022.
- EOSC onboarding of U1 and A3 thematic services has been rescheduled for Q1 2022 (instead of Q4 2021), due to fine-tuning of the services and their integration with NEANIAS core services. The same applies for Atmo-Seism service under A2 – Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions.
- The S2 service (Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional image) will not be separately onboarded to EOSC as its functionality is delivered through the Vialactea and ADAM-SPACE services, which are already available on EOSC.
- The SPACE-ML AstroML service under S3 will not be onboarded to EOSC as its functionality is included in the SPACE-ML CAESAR service.

As for the onboarding of NEANIAS core services to EOSC, the following are noted:

⁹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/vd-maps/details>

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

- One core service (VD-Maps under C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery) has been onboarded to EOSC in December 2021 according to the plan presented in Deliverable in D8.3.
- The onboarding plans of some other core services have been clarified:
 - C3.1, C3.2 and C4.4 services won't be onboarded to EOSC.
 - C3.3 service (Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod) is expected to be made available on EOSC marketplace in Q1 2022.
- The onboarding plans of the rest of NEANIAS core services (C3.4, VD-VisIVO and VD-Splotch under C4.1, C4.2) are still under investigation. Issues under consideration by the providers of these services include indicatively the availability of similar services on EOSC marketplace and the possibility of a user supporting the operation of the services with own computing resources. The dependency/ relationship of VD-VisIVO and VD-Splotch services with the C4.2 (Visualisation Gateway) service is also an issue under investigation of the providers of these services, which impacts the finalisation of their EOSC onboarding plans.

3.2. Integration with EOSC services

The following table presents up-to-date information on the integration/ connection of NEANIAS (core) services with EOSC equivalent/ relevant ones:

EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service	Status / Comments
1.EOSC Portal		NEANIAS catalogue portal	Completed. A prototype implementation of the integration of the NEANIAS catalogue portal with the EOSC one through the EOSC API has been completed. Through this integration, changes on services on the NEANIAS catalogue portal are propagated to the EOSC marketplace. In the next period we will work more for the full integration with the EOSC APIs.
2.Federation services	EOSC AAI	NEANIAS AAI	Terms of Use and Privacy statement

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service	Status / Comments
			pending for integration.
	Availability and reliability monitoring	NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure	The integration of EOSC monitoring with NEANIAS thematic and core services is ongoing. The NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure is being used to complement EOSC monitoring with support for, e.g., whitebox monitoring.
	Usage accounting (compute and storage)	NEANIAS Accounting	No integration is currently planned.
	Helpdesk (ticketing system)	NEANIAS Helpdesk system	No interface. NEANIAS will use its own Helpdesk system. Integration to be revisited in the future.
3. Research data management services	Compute, storage, transfer, analysis, etc.)	GARR Cloud	No integration is currently planned in NEANIAS.
	Zenodo (research output catalogue + PID)	Service Catalogue Research Data Repository and Catalogue Data Management based on ARGOS	Argos is integrated with Zenodo.
4. Service Management System (SMS)	EOSC SMS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service management processes defined using FitSM • Respective implementation tools 	NEANIAS SMS defined in D8.2 [4]: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service management processes and procedures defined using FitSM 	Although separate than the EOSC SMS, the NEANIAS SMS was developed following the same principles and framework as the EOSC one.

D8.4 EOSC integration activities report (interim)

EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service	Status / Comments
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation tools defined and developed (Section 2.3 and D8.2) 	
5. Service pricing: Pay-for-use ordering	No pay-for-use ordering, or any other financial transaction support, in EOSC's current or envisaged offerings	---	To be investigated by service providers outside of NEANIAS project
6. Service pricing: Ordering with computing resources provided by the user	EOSC Compute Platform provided by EGI-ACE project	---	Investigation of the possibility to use EOSC Compute Platform based on the plan presented in section 2.4.2

4. Conclusions

Since the first release of EOSC integration plan in Deliverable D8.1 in July 2020 and its update in Deliverable D8.3 [1] in August 2021, a lot of developments both at the EOSC level and at NEANIAS services have been realised. However, the approach for EOSC integration still remains valid, and guides all relevant activities performed in the NEANIAS context. This approach is adjusted to EOSC developments where needed and the new/ modified/ upgraded characteristics of NEANIAS thematic services, when new releases are made available.

As derived from the information presented in Chapter 3, the integration of NEANIAS with EOSC is progressing quite smoothly and according, with minor deviations, to the plan presented in Deliverable D8.3:

1. Thematic services are in the process of onboarding EOSC, with six (6) of them already available on EOSC marketplace, one (1) additional service in the process of being onboarded and the remaining ones (four) having planned EOSC onboarding until the end of 2021 and Q1 2022. This way, the project is not very far from achieving its target to onboard nine (9) thematic services to EOSC.
2. Providers of NEANIAS core services have further processed and clarified their plans for EOSC onboarding; one (1) core service is already available on EOSC marketplace, the onboarding of an additional one is planned for Q1 2022, while the plans for four (4) core services are still under investigation.
3. NEANIAS core services have already been aligned with EOSC ones in the areas of AAI, accounting, monitoring for the purposes of future / potential integration. Moreover, the integration of NEANIAS Research Data Management services with corresponding EOSC ones, has progressed significantly and is already providing the platform to thematic services for bringing FAIR data onto EOSC.
4. The NEANIAS service management system has been defined and made available to all NEANIAS service providers for application. On top, a helpdesk system has been setup and customised in order to support the execution of the processes and procedures defined by the NEANIAS SMS. Services that go through the process of EOSC onboarding are expected to be integrated with the helpdesk system.

As the EOSC landscape is constantly evolving and NEANIAS services continue to mature, NEANIAS will stay open for new integration opportunities offered by EOSC, and reconsider/update its own integration roadmap as needed in the future. D8.5 (due at month 32) will be the next (and final) formal checkpoint for assessing the progress of activities towards EOSC integration.

References

- [1] NEANIAS project, Deliverable D8.3: EOSC integration plan (final)
- [2] Horovod [<https://eng.uber.com/horovod/>]
- [3] ARGO monitoring [<https://argoeu.github.io/>]
- [4] NEANIAS project, Deliverable D8.2: EOSC service model
- [5] EC Digital Future Policies: Open Data. [<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/open-data>]
- [6] Wilkinson, M. D. et al, (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>]
- [7] ARGOS service [<https://argos.openaire.eu/>]
- [8] Zenodo [<https://zenodo.org/>]
- [9] OAI-PMH [<https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>]
- [10] Zenodo REST API [<https://developers.zenodo.org>]
- [11] FitSM Standards for lightweight IT service management [<https://www.fitsm.eu/>]
- [12] ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018, Information technology — Service management — Part 1: Service management system requirements, [<https://www.iso.org/standard/70636.html>]
- [13] IT Infrastructure Library [<https://www.axelos.com/best-practice-solutions/itil>]
- [14] NEANIAS project, Deliverable D9.3: Draft business plan, preliminary business plan as input to other tasks, business innovation and stakeholder engagement activities